

Vector Heuristics for Dual Coordinate Sum Sorting Problem

Mirzakhmet Syzdykov
Satbayev University, Almaty, Kazakhstan
mspmail598@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The $X + Y$ sum problem as observed wasn't solved before, so we provide a fast and simple solution to this problem using algebraic properties of the vector as well as the general case.

INTRODUCTION

The problem is in general still unsolved and plays a role in effective optimization.

SOLUTION

We simply sort the items by the normal vector distance to the line $X + Y$ going through the given point.

This simply gives the minimal possible running time on average as $O(n \cdot \log(n))$.

CONCLUSION

The above case can be extended to the problem where the normal vector of a line is given with arbitrary weights which open new horizons to the studying of the application and theoretical acquisition of this problem.

The sorting problem for dual coords can be solved in minimal possible time $O(n)$ by converting it to co-NP problem as integer sorting.

REFERENCES

Klarreich, Erica. "Multiplication hits the speed limit." *Communications of the ACM* 63.1 (2019): 11-13.